

A Tale of Gender Discrimination in Mahesh Dattain's Play Tara

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Abstract

Mahesh Dattani's play Tara deals with the theme of gender discrimination in the society. The present paper discusses and analyses how Dattani's has shown the issues of marginalization of women in this play. It is a moving story of conjoined twins, Tara and Chandan. The play highlights how much a boy is given more importance than a girl in an Indian family. Dattani considers gender discrimination as unnatural and moral beliefs connected with principles bring out complex and multi-dimensional nature of issue. The play pictures the unacceptable and strong influence of giving importance only to men in the collective awareness of society. These values of socialization which makes women weak physically and emotionally. Men always treat women cruelly without giving them the same freedom and rights. In the play, Bharati the mother of Tara spoils life of her daughter and later suffers from the guilt of her inhuman act. Her guilt leads her to madness and creates problem in the family also. Dattani also expresses the innocent attitude of society towards the differently abled persons. The misuse of science and technology is expressed through the character Dr. Thakkar.

Keywords: Discrimination, Marginalization, Conjoined, Multi-dimensional, Transplantation.

Author

Mahesh Dattani is a famous Indian Writer. He was born on 7th August 1958, Bangalore, India. He is also a playwright, screen writer, film maker and stage director. As a writer, he was awarded the prestigious Sahitya Academic award in 1998. His works are, Final Solution (1993), Dance Like a Man (1989), Bravely Fought the Queen (1991), On a Muggy Night in Mumbai (1998), Tara (1990), 30 Days in September (2001), The Big Fat City (2012), The Murder that Never was (2000), Where There is a Will (1988), Brief Candle (2009). Tara was one of the first Indian plays in English to highlight the dangers of gender discrimination in our society.

Atale of Gender Discrimination

Tara is a unique play in Indian Writing in English. The play moves around the life of the conjoined twins of different sex. Doctor says, the conjoined twins are usually of the same sex. The play TARA gains the attraction of the audience because the conjoined twins are of different gender. Dattani has woven into the play are issues of class and community and the clash between traditional and modern lifestyle.

The play is divided into two acts. The play starts as Chandan from London where he is known Dan, he is narrating his childhood days and the movements that he spent with his sister Tara. He thinks to write about his childhood but when he takes the pen, he gets diverted and writes the story of Tara. The whole play revolves around Chandan and Tara; they are Siamese twins at birth.

DAN: Is it a rare phenomenon?

DR. THAKKAR: Twins as such are not so rare, the chance.....

DAN: What about Siamese twins?

DR. THAKKAR: Conjoined twins are quite rare. I think one in every fifty thousand twin conceptions could have a probability of containing this....defect. (11)

The play throws light on the increasing incidents of the crime, killing a baby and widening the space between the male and the female child. This play is not only a story of the protagonist but it is the life of every girl child born in Indian family whether it is a village or in a city.

The play is about the separation of the conjoined twins and the problem faced by the protagonist is also highlighted. The idea of separation of the twins arises to the parents because they are of different sex. It becomes necessary to separate the twins where there is no reason, but their parents thought that it would be a benefited one for their daughter and son. After their separation they could lead a happy and wonderful life. They thought Tara and Chandan could have a bright future without depending on each other both physically and emotionally.

The main aim of the separation of the conjoined twins is motivated favor of the boy Chandan. In this play Mahesh Dattani expresses the fact that even now the educated parents of the 21st century have the different motives and ideas for a girl and a boy. Where Tara becomes the prey for their parents activities in order to support Chandan.

They have planned for the major operation between Tara and Chandan. But the doctor have discovered three legs between both instead of four legs. The doctor mentions to their parents that the two belongs to Tara and another one belongs to Chandan. The doctors suggests that Chandan's another leg should be replaced by the artificial leg. But Tara's mother and her grandfather wants Chandan two legs and the one should be borrowed from Tara. The doctor explains that it is so risk to do like that. Finally Dr. Thakkar and his team had accepted to take risk of separating the leg from Tara and transplanted to Chandan.

Dr. Thakkar accepts to perform the operation willingly because of his own personal benefits. The family members of Tara wanted to make Chandan stronger physically. Tara and her future is not given importance by her parents.

The reason for preferring male child is that he will carry all the burden and he will be the bread winner of the family. On the contrary, the word 'girl' means "dowry, burden, and lot of expenditure". This situation becomes worse when, the child is physically challenged or if the girl has any other mental disorder. The mentality of the society is that if a girl is physically challenged or mentally disorder means they think that giving dowry is of no use. She prefers to remain unmarried and they feel that she is a burden to the family.

Finally, the surgeon is ready for operation because of money. After that they fears about the operation which results in Chandan becomes disability while Tara is already a disabled one. The thing which hurts Tara the most is the preference given to his brother Chandan because he belongs to the gender male. Tara also realizes that she is not given any opportunity to be treated as a normal human being because she is female. This play deals with the real circumstances in which all the girl child born in Indian family are facing so many problems if there is a boy in the family, the girl child is ill treated consciously or unconsciously by giving all the privileges to the boy child. Erin Mee says,

“Tara is the story of a conjoined twins separated at birth, by a surgical procedure intended to favor the boy over the girl. Told through boy’s reflections on his childhood memories, Tara’s story is also a reflection of the feminine struggle for expression both physically and emotionally in a patriarchal Indian society”(319).

Tara feels that her father’s favorite is Chandan, most of the time his father talks about only Chandan’s career and his going to Abroad. This highlights how the gender conflicts and gender differences are to be realized by Tara unconsciously. There was kidney transplantation for Chandan, after finishing the transplantation; he wants to go the college. Chandan does not want to go without Tara to the college. He is not ready to go alone but he wants Tara to accompany him. Tara and Chandan do not think about gender discrimination. But Mr. and Mrs. Patel do not think that both of them are equal. But Chandan is not like that, he has a special concern towards her sister Tara, and he thinks that both are equal.

TARA: Yes, but I will soon be going in for surgery.

ROOPA: Oh, how sad! On your leg.

TARA: No. A kidney transplant.

ROOPA: Gosh! (18).

This play shows how the girl who is physically challenged has to sacrifice herself to the family. This makes herself to feel distressed and feel lonely. She feels dejected because her father does not care for her and her future. She asks her father that she need to meet Chandan and spent some time with him her father says that how it is possible. Tara feels that her father is only worried about Chandan and his career.

Bharati: I wish your father would pay more attention to Tara.

Chandan: He does, he doesn’t like to show his affection.

Bharati: Don’t tell me about your father, he is more worried about your career than hers (28).

In this play Dattani expresses how the girl child is not given importance and made to be under the control of someone and the decision of their own is not given any importance.

Dr.Thakkar: Our greatest challenge would be to keep the girl alive. Nature wanted to kill her. We could not allow it.

Roopa: Tara! Come on out! We want to talk to you! (56). though Tara is the main character of the play, she has been a target to the social favor against woman. She also has all the capacity of a new developing woman. She is more interested, active to achieve something in her life. She has high thoughts and aims to achieve but it becomes impossible because of her physical problem .She stands as feeling angry against the society. She has some kind of hatred towards the society. Tara’s world is too small, that is her parents and brother. Tara likes to live a shining life. But she does not get any opportunities as her brother gets. She thinks about the modern society, with all sorts of technical development. Even though her parents are educated, they showed difference between the boy child and the girl child. Tara’s father particularly feels that giving equal opportunities to a boy and a girl is not applicable in the society.

Tara is a girl who becomes as a prey to the family members by accepting all the decisions taken by then. In this Play Tara Mahesh Dattani has intertwined two theme which makes the play more powerful. Firstly Tara is suppressed in all the activities and the importance is given to a boy child than the girl child. Secondly, He also shows the greed of the doctor. Thakkar in this play. The play Tara swings to the actions in the past in Mumbai where Chandan and Tara had spent their childhood days. Erin Mee says, “The main point remains in Tara is the play about the bias of the parents towards a girl child. In it Dan discovers the neglected half on himself as a means becoming whole”.

Dattani's Tara presents the real life situation of women in the Indian family. And how they are controlled by the male. In India gender discrimination plays a vital role in the modern society. Tara has so many aims to achieve in her life. But she does not even get any opportunity to prove herself in the world. In this play even Tara's mother does not support Tara. Her mother also supported her son Chandan; she gives importance only to him. In the modern society also people think that a woman or a girl should be under the control of the man and she should obey all their commands. In the present days all women are obeying others and controlled by father or husband or son and they are losing their own identity.

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